

Probabilistic Representation: Additive Statistically Approximate Distributions

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Abstract

End-to-end explainable Bayes deep-learning research works when there are products of many inputs. But, multiplication is computationally time-consuming (and there can be quantisation errors if there are many multiplications on a 32-bit computer). So, a pure additive deep-learning-network is being used using logarithms (which can be used as hash-maps or so). A training process and a local approximation theorem are being proposed. The training process includes backpropagation too.

Note: The results have not been discussed. I am planning to discuss this using the peer-reviewed version of this.

1 Introduction

The main goal of this research is to use logarithm version of Approximated Bayes Approximate Distributions (ABAD). The hypothesis is this: log-ABAD can be trained using either Backpropagation or Blind Descent. A matrix version of this training process is being proposed as a solution for efficient compute.

2 Prior Work

Approximated Bayes Approximate Distributions (ABAD) uses direct multiplications (and does not eliminate multiplication process completely).[3] The proposed statistical algorithm is "differentiable". So, efficient matrix backpropagation can be used.[2] Also, Blind Descent can be used as the logarithm can have unexpected output for certain input (like zero input for natural logarithm).[1]

3 Logarithm of negative input

If m is a negative real number,

$$m = re^{i\theta} \Rightarrow \log_2 m = \log_2 re^{i\theta} = \log_2 r + \log_2 e^{i\theta} = \log_2 |m| + i\theta \log_2 e \quad (1)$$

$$\therefore \log_2 m = \log_2 |m| + i\theta \log_2 e \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} e^{i\theta} = 1 & \quad \text{if } \theta = 2n\pi = n(2\pi) \\ e^{i\theta} = -1 & \quad \text{if } \theta = (n + \frac{1}{2})(2\pi) \end{aligned} \Bigg| n \in \text{integers} \quad (3)$$

If m is negative,

$$\therefore \log_2 m = \log_2 |m| + i(n + \frac{1}{2})(2\pi) \log_2 e \quad (4)$$

So,

$$\log_2 m = \log_2 |m| + i(2n\pi + \pi) \log_2 e \quad (5)$$

Assuming $n = 0$,

$$\boxed{\log_2 m = \log_2 |m| + (i\pi) \log_2 e}$$

4 Local Approximation Theorem

Note: In this statistics research, $i = \sqrt{-1}$ and i can be an index of a matrix also (depending on the context).

4.1 Assumption 1

$x \sim U(-\epsilon, \epsilon); \epsilon \rightarrow 0$

$x \sim$ Identical and Independent Uniform Random Distribution

4.2 Assumption 2

$|x| \ll |w|$ (or $|x_i| \ll |w_i| \quad \forall i$)

4.3 Assumption 3

x is both left differentiable and right differentiable at 0.

4.4 Assumption 4

$w_i \neq 0 \quad \forall i$ and $x_i + w_i \neq 0 \quad \forall i$

4.5 Local Approximation Theorem Proof

We can assume that we have a power-series.

$$\log(x + w) = c_0 + c_1x + c_2x^2 + c_3x^3 + c_4x^4 + \dots \quad (6)$$

$$x = 0 \Rightarrow \log(w) = c_0 \quad (7)$$

Differentiating using x, we have this:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \log(x + w) = \frac{d}{dx} [c_0 + c_1x + c_2x^2 + c_3x^3 + c_4x^4 + \dots] \quad (8)$$

Setting x = 0, we have this:

$$(x + w)^{-1} = c_1 \Rightarrow c_1 = w^{-1} \quad (9)$$

$$\boxed{\log(x + w) \simeq \log(w) + \frac{x}{w}}$$

So,

$$\Sigma_i \log(x_i + w_i) = \Sigma_i \log(w_i) + \Sigma_i \frac{x_i}{w_i} \quad (10)$$

$\frac{1}{w_i}$ is like a "multiplicative" weight.

$$\boxed{\therefore \text{ReLU}[B + \Sigma_i \log(x_i + w_i)] \simeq \text{ReLU}[(B + \Sigma_i \log(w_i)) + (\Sigma_i \frac{x_i}{w_i})]}$$

5 ReLU notes and relation with Bayes Multiplication

ReLU is being used so that we can consider only real component and ignore the imaginary component. However, any standard activation function can be used (but, they may involve complex numbers compute).

$$\text{LayerOutput} = \text{ReLU}[\Pi_i(w_i + x_i) + B] \quad (11)$$

is locally approximate.

$$\text{LayerOutput} = \text{ReLU}[B + \log \Pi_i(w_i + x_i)] \quad (12)$$

is the new log-network that is being proposed (which is also locally approximate; But, this has better compute options).

$$\boxed{\log \Pi_i t_i = \Sigma_i \log t_i \Rightarrow \text{LayerOutput} = \text{ReLU}[B + \Sigma_i \log(x_i + w_i)]}$$

6 Backpropagation

This is important as B is important. So, the "errors" may have to be minimised (especially for B).

$$Loss = \frac{\partial L}{\partial w} \quad \text{and} \quad B + \Sigma_i \log(x_i + w_i) = y \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial w_{layer}} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial activation_output} \times \frac{\partial activation_output}{\partial y} \times \frac{\partial activation_input}{\partial w_{layer}} \quad (14)$$

$$\boxed{\frac{\partial y}{\partial w_i} = \frac{\partial \log(x_i + w_i)}{\partial w_i} = \frac{1}{x_i + w_i} \mid \frac{\partial y}{\partial B} = 1}$$

Note:

If $x_i + w_i \simeq 0$, then, both layer output compute and gradient compute can have problems. So, if $|x_i + w_i| \simeq 0$, $x_i + w_i = 1 \Rightarrow w_i = 1 - x_i$.

(we set w to be 1 - x if that is so)

7 Blind Descent

npRandomChoice is option 1. The idea is to use the combination of learning-rate and "choice of random weights" to update. The learning rate can be 2^{-1} to 2^{-16} . The "number of weights" (which need to be updated) can be 2^z where z can be a natural number. [Then, we can use coordinate descent until no weight changes for an iteration or when we have a "maximum" number of iterations (like 65536 or so)]

3BlindDescent is option 2. The idea is to try pseudo-random weights 3 times and if both the total loss and losses of any of two attempts are lesser than the original loss, then, the weights of the first attempt are saved.

An "extended" idea is to use some number of attempts and some number of attempts which have losses lesser than the original loss. (like 8 and 5) If we happen to have total loss of all those attempts lesser than the original loss, then, we can save the weights of the first attempt.

Note: Off-the-shelf "autograd" software library is not being used for these experiments to avoid any unexpected gradient compute problems. [But, autograd may be much easier to work with]

8 Matrix version of Backpropagation

Latent Output

$$y = B + \Sigma_i \log(x_i + w_i) \Rightarrow y_j = B_j + \Sigma_i \log(x_i + w_{ij}) \quad (15)$$

This is meant for GPU compute. For each layer,

1. (weight) $w \rightarrow$ 2D matrix (i along height and j along width)
2. (input) $x \rightarrow$ A flattened vector (not batch) repeated across the width j times [A flattened vector transformed into a column of w's height]
3. $B \rightarrow$ Bias [A flattened vector along width]
4. $\frac{\partial L}{\partial y_j} \rightarrow$ Differential loss vector [A flattened vector along width]
5. $y_j \rightarrow$ Latent Output vector (without activation layer) [A flattened vector along width]

In the equation of latent output, if we consider input as the output of previous layer, then, for calculus, we have two aspects: 1. weight and 2. latent output or input. So, if we need to compute the gradient of loss at the input, (one of the input nodes) we need the sum of derivatives of loss of all weights (connected to that input node) which are used to compute latent outputs (of that layer).

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial w_{ij}} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial y_j} \times \frac{\partial y_j}{\partial w_{ij}} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial y_j} \times \frac{1}{x_i + w_{ij}} \quad (16)$$

$$\Sigma_j \frac{\partial L}{\partial w_{ij}} = \Sigma_j \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial y_j} \times \frac{1}{x_i + w_{ij}} \right) \quad (17)$$

This is the gradient of loss at the input (node). This is $\frac{\partial L}{\partial y_j}$, a loss that we can backpropagate from (From $\frac{\partial L}{\partial y_j}$ of previous layer). A similar explanation is supposed to help us compute the gradient of loss for B.

References

- [1] Akshat Gupta and Prasad N R, “*Blind Descent: A Prequel to Gradient Descent*”, Vol. 783 Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering, ICDSMLA, Springer (2020)
- [2] David E. Rumelhart, Geoffrey E. Hinton, Ronald J. Williams, *Learning representations by back-propagating errors*, Vol. 323, Nature, 1986
- [3] Prasad N R, *Posterior Regression: Approximated Statistically Approximate Distributions*, Zenodo, Dec. 18, 2023. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10402509.